

CUTTING STRATEGIES OF LONG FIBER PATCH PREFORMS FOR STRUCTURES WITH COMPLEX FIBER ARCHITECTURE

Bernhard Horn¹, Sebastian Sattler¹, Christoph Ebel¹ and Klaus Drechsler¹

¹Institute for Carbon Composites, Technische Universität München
Boltzmannstraße 15, DE-85748 Garching, Germany
Email: horn@lcc.mw.tum.de, web page: <http://www.lcc.mw.tum.de>

Keywords: Curvilinear load path, Long fiber reinforcement, Fiber patch placement

ABSTRACT

Load path optimized design is one way to reduce fiber consumption and therefore lead to lower manufacturing cost and weight. Continuous fibers in the form of rovings or tapes are typically placed according to load path. Typical technologies which are using this method (e.g. automated fiber placement or tailored fiber placement) are limited when it comes to small radii of curvature. The use of fiber patches with a specific length is an approach to overcome those limitations. A fiber tape is cut into patches which then can be placed independently in position and orientation of other patches. This enables high flexibility in fiber positioning. Since the patches are placed typically placed in a line, the size of gaps and overlaps between two neighboring patches of the same layer differs depending on the shape of the patch and the curvature of the allocated load path. Those gaps and overlaps are negatively influencing the mechanical properties and affect the impregnation behavior due to locally varying areal weight. One approach to avoid gaps and overlaps is to have a patch with a shape according to the load path trajectory. This paper presents studies on the influence of different patch geometries on tensile strength and stiffness and gives further insight into the failure mechanisms of patched laminates.

1 INTRODUCTION

The main cost drivers in current composite manufacturing are a high amount of labor and expensive base materials. Increasing automation in carbon composite manufacturing has the potential to reduce the cost of composite parts by up to 30-40 % whereas manufacturing of fiber material has potential to lower cost by another 25-30 % [1]. Since material cost of a typical composite application is between 40-45 %, a significant cost reduction requires an increase in degree of automation while fiber consumption has to be lowered.

The approach of load optimized design is an efficient way to reduce fiber consumption since fiber is only applied where it is locally needed. Nevertheless, load path optimized lay-up design requires high flexibility in fiber positioning. For large structures with simple fiber architecture use of endless unidirectional fiber tape is a proven concept in industrial application when using automated placement processes. However those manufacturing technologies are limited when it comes to small structures with complex fiber architecture and small load path radii [2]. Local fiber buckling induced by in-plane bending deformation limits path curvature to a minimum radius around 800 mm depending on the width of the tape. For smaller radii an undulation on the inner side of the tape occurs which strongly decreases the mechanical properties like stiffness and strength [3].

An approach to overcome these limitations is the use of long fiber patches made of spread and bindered rovings instead of quasi-continuous fiber material. The technology which uses this method is called fiber patch placement (FPP) [4]. A curvilinear load path is covered by a line of long fiber patches and can thereby follow a broader range of curvatures with a smaller minimum radius compared to continuous fibers without causing buckling of the yarns. This effect is illustrated on Figure 1. The fiber distribution in cross section becomes inhomogeneous for fiber tape and small radii (left picture) while it stays almost constant when using fiber patches (right picture).

Figure 1: Difference in steering for fiber tape and fiber patch

Compared to a typical fiber placement process with continuous fibers the layup design of long fiber patches is more difficult due to the limited fiber length. At the end of each fiber patch the load needs to be transferred from one layer to the neighboring one by shear forces. This requires at least two layers which therefore is a basic condition for patched laminates. The area where the load is redirected has to be tailored according to the mechanical properties desired. The resulting stacking sequence is called patch pattern. On Figure 2 the theoretical effect of different patch patterns on the tensile strength of a coupon is illustrated. One patch of each layer is illustrated by a line, the discontinuity by a gap. For example 1 all discontinuities are positioned on top of each other. The maximum tensile strength is thereby defined by the one of the resin system which is the weakest link between two patches. On the other hand in example 4 the stacking sequence is optimized to maximize the distance between two discontinuities which results in higher tensile strength. Here load can be transferred from one layer to the next one by shear forces as previously described.

Figure 2: Influence of patch pattern on tensile strength (cf. [4])

To enable load path optimized design the patches are placed in a way that they follow the load path as exactly as possible. Since those paths are usually curved with different radii, gaps and overlaps are occurring at the discontinuities when using rectangular patches (see Figure 3, left sketch). With smaller radii of the patch lines the degree of gaps and overlaps are increasing. This is leading to undulations in the laminate which are affecting the mechanical properties and changes the areal weight locally. Due to this the impregnation behavior or surface quality depending on the impregnation method chosen, can get influenced. One approach to reduce this effect is to use a round cutting geometry [4]. This geometry works well for light curvatures but for small radii a gap and overlapping effect occurs as well (see Figure 3, sketch in the middle). However, the effect is smaller as it is for rectangular patches. Additionally the precise cutting of round patches is difficult due to the symmetric cutting edge. The patches are cut by a rigid blade in a stamping movement. If the tape is not perfectly aligned under the blade, an asymmetric cut is resulting. On one hand this can be improved by using a more advanced cutting concept, e.g. a laser cutting system, but on the other hand this increases

machine cost significantly. Therefore the use a straight cutting edge is preferred to increase robustness and to keep the machine cost down.

A new approach to completely avoid gaps and overlaps is to constantly change the cutting angle to always have an optimal angle depending on the curvature of the load path (see Figure 3, right sketch).

Figure 3: Gaps and overlaps for different patch geometries: rectangular (left), round (middle), variable angle (right)

Due to the necessary stress redistribution at the discontinuity between two patches an effect on the mechanical properties is expected depended on the type of cutting geometry. Therefore this paper presents an investigation on different cutting geometries and their effect on tensile strength and Young's modulus and the failure mechanism of patched coupons. A similar investigation has already been conducted by Hofer [5]. In this work patched samples (4 layer, 50 mm patch length) made of carbon fiber weave with 470 g/sqm were tested for tensile strength, bending and energy absorption during Charpy impact test. The results showed a weak proportional dependency of the cutting angle on the tensile strength and an increased energy absorption for small cutting angles due to an increased area of fracture. But since only unidirectional fiber tape with low areal weight is used for FPP applications the results cannot be transferred directly. As Wisnom already showed, the mechanical properties are decreasing significantly with higher areal weight and the delamination behavior changes [6]. Therefore for laminates with a higher areal weight this effect might dominate the influence of the cutting angle.

2 MATERIALS AND METHOD

For investigating the influence of cutting geometries on tensile strength and Young's modulus the tensile test is chosen. The specimens are designed according to EN ISO 527-4 specimen type 2 with 150 mm free length [7]. The width is changed to 15mm due to manufacturing purposes (see Figure 4). Each specimen consists of 30 layers of tape. Due to the constant length of 60 mm per patch more than one discontinuity would appear per layer. Since the discontinuity is the weakest area of the specimen it is sufficient to adapt the length for each patch to have only one discontinuity per layer. Due to this modification the area where the failure is expected can be narrowed. Typically the pattern is calculated by dividing the chosen patch length by the amount of layers per pattern and then distribute the discontinuities in multiplications of this distance between the layers so that in thickness direction there is no discontinuity at the same point. Former experiments showed that an amount of five layers per pattern already leads to sufficient results. Since 60 mm is the standard patch length for FPP the corresponding overlap length is therefore 12 mm (see Figure 5).

Figure 4: Dimensions of the specimens

Figure 5: Lay-up sequence of each specimen (30 Layers)

Four different cutting geometries are chosen for this investigation. Rectangular patch geometry (a) as standard geometry for fiber patch placement laminates, round (b) as one approach for curved patch path and 45°- (c) and 30°- (d) cutting angle as two examples for the new approach with variable cutting angles. The angles are chosen to cover a broad range of possible cutting angles. The four geometries are sketched in Figure 6. In the following the specimens are named depending on the cutting geometry, e.g. specimen consisting of patches cut in 45° angle will be called 45°-specimen.

Figure 6: Investigated patch geometries a) round b) rectangular c) 45° d) 30°

The materials selected for this investigation are Oxeon Textreme HTS45 unidirectional carbon fiber tape with 20 mm width and SIKA CR80/CH10 as epoxy resin system. The areal weight of the tape is 80 g/m². Material data is shown on Table 1. All specimen have been infiltrated at room temperature using VARI process and have been tempered afterwards at 55 °C for 16 h to increase the strength of the resin system according to the material data sheet.

Material	Type	Manufacturer	Tensile Strength	Young's-modulus	Density
Textreme HTS 40	Spread tow tape	Oxeon	4300 MPa	240 GPa	1.77
CR 80 - CH 10	Resin and hardener	Sika	69 MPa	3.3 GPa	1.16

Table 1: Material data

The tensile tests are executed with a Hegewald & Peschke inspect 250 universal testing machine and a movement speed of 1 mm/min. To determine the strain and stresses of the coupon a digital image correlation system (ARAMIS by GOM, picture rate: 1 fps) is used and positioned in front of the coupon. The failure is additionally observed by a high speed camera (63000 fps) which is positioned in 90° to the ARAMIS system and has its focus on one of the coupon side surfaces. This surface is colored white to increase the contrast between specimen surface and an occurring crack and thereby

highlight the crack propagation during failure. Five specimens per cutting geometry are tested until final failure.

Figure 7: Testing setup with ARAMIS system and high-speed camera

3 RESULTS

To simplify the comparison of the mechanical properties all specimens have been standardized towards a fiber volume fraction of 60 %. The fiber volume fraction of each specimen has been determined by measuring the weight of each specimen before and after infiltration and then calculating the value with respect to the density of each material. The values are listed in Table 2 and Table 3 and. In the following only standardized values are presented and compared.

Geometry	Specimen number	Fiber volume fraction	Tensile Strength [MPa]	Tensile Strength (stand.) [MPa]	Young's modulus (abs.) [GPa]	Young's modulus (stand) [GPa]
Rectangular	1	61,9%	Invalid		147,99	143,37
	2	62,9%	1.380,13	151,39	144,46	146,11
	3	62,6%	1.374,30	154,25	147,75	149,46
	4	64,2%	1.366,23	150,96	141,03	142,52
	5	64,6%	1.280,93	151,33	140,52	141,98
Round	1	62,1%	1.332,23	144,71	139,92	141,59
	2	61,5%	1.299,86	145,16	141,70	143,45
	3	61,0%	1.354,28	146,83	144,50	146,32
	4	61,8%	1.346,35	148,65	144,28	146,02
	5	60,6%	1.319,45	141,86	140,40	142,20

Table 2: Overview over specimens and corresponding testing results (1)

Geometry	Specimen number	Fiber volume fraction	Tensile Strength [MPa]	Tensile Strength (stand.) [MPa]	Young's modulus (abs.) [GPa]	Young's modulus (stand) [GPa]
30	1	61,5%	1.457,35	1.422,19	145,73	142,21
	2	60,0%	1.379,40	1.378,89	145,71	145,66
	3	61,1%	1.397,83	1.371,92	149,04	146,28
	4	63,1%	1.420,01	1.349,90	150,24	142,82
	5	63,5%	1.371,43	1.296,19	Invalid	
45	1	62,3%	1.326,64	1.277,95	149,31	143,83
	2	62,3%	1.330,91	1.282,06	147,82	142,40
	3	62,3%	1.347,16	1.297,72	150,18	144,66
	4	62,1%	1.447,40	1.398,18	149,25	144,17
	5	59,5%	1.374,33	1.385,80	invalid	

Table 3: Overview over specimens and corresponding testing results (2)

The investigation showed very similar results for each cutting geometry (compare Table 3). Results for tensile strength can be seen in Figure 8. The mean values for all sets of the five specimens and standard deviation are shown in the left diagram. The means for tensile strength and Young's modulus are very close together and a clear trend is not immediately obvious. To reveal dependencies the two sample t-test as a statistic method is used [8]. Here the null hypothesis that the sample means are equal is tested on a 5 % significance level. The resulting p-value gives the probability to do an alpha error which means the null hypothesis is rejected although it is correct. In this case that means that the means are equal but are interpreted as different. Since a 5 % significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) is chosen the accepted p-value has to be lower than this value.

When regarding the 95 %-confidence interval for the different geometries (Figure 8, right diagram) it can be seen that some intervals of different specimen groups are overlapping. As a remark, the scale is adjusted to highlight the intervals. The only non-overlapping areas are between round and 30°-specimen (p-value: 0.028) respectively between rectangular and 30° (p-value: 0.039). Here the null hypothesis that the means are equal can be rejected on the $\alpha = 5\%$ significance level between those types because $p < \alpha$. When comparing those intervals it can be seen that there is a tendency for higher strength of specimen cut under smaller angles. Maximum strength is improved from 1350.4 MPa for rectangular geometry to 1405.2 MPa for 30° which is an increase by 4.01 %.

Figure 8: Mean tensile strength of specimens with standard deviation (left) and the corresponding 95% confidence interval (right) for different cutting geometries

The means of Young's modulus are very similar as well but no dependency could be identified (see Figure 9). The confidence intervals are overlapping and the t-test in this case showed p-values between 0.188 and 0.794 which means the null hypothesis cannot be rejected in any case ($p \gg \alpha$).

Figure 9: Mean Young's modulus of specimens with standard deviation (left) and the corresponding 95% confidence interval (right) for different cutting geometries

The specimens showed similar failure behavior independent of the cutting geometry. The failure started with a delamination in the outer plies which were increasing with higher tension applied and thereby causing a reduction of the cross section of the specimen. Once the tension exceeded the maximum tensile strength the specimen failed. A tested specimen is shown on Figure 10. The former shape of the cutting geometry (marked with a red dotted ellipse) can still be seen which is an indication for an interlaminar failure.

Figure 10: Tested specimen with marked cutting edges (30 °-specimen)

As a remark to the previous picture, due to the high tension in the specimen before failure this energy is causing multiple delaminations once the failure occurs and thereby leading to fanned out specimens which makes it more difficult to identify failure modes afterwards.

4 DISCUSSION

Different considerations were made to identify the influences of the cutting geometry. First consideration regards the geometry of the cutting edge. It can be described by the cutting angle and the length of the cut which are normally connected geometrically. Typically a failure starts within a resin rich discontinuity. With increasing length of the cutting edge the area where a failure can start increases as well. Therefore by introducing a longer cutting edge the mechanical properties are becoming higher. The cutting length of the round cutting geometry is 16.7 mm, for rectangular 15 mm, for 30 °-specimens 30 mm and for 45 °-specimen it is 21.2 mm. The mean of tensile strength and the cutting length are shown in Figure 11. To highlight the differences the scale is once again adjusted. Based on those results a tendency of higher strength values for longer cutting edges (smaller angles) can be seen. Due to the limited data further interpretations cannot be made at this point. When having a look at the Young's modulus no dependency can be identified since the data is too similar (see Figure 12).

Figure 11: Comparison between mean tensile strength (with std. deviation) and cutting length for different cutting geometries

Figure 12: Comparison between mean Young's modulus (with std. deviation) and cutting length for different cutting geometries

The second consideration regards the overlapping length of the patches. As shown in Figure 5 the overlapping length is the distance between the discontinuities of two neighboring layers and describes the area where tension in fiber direction has to be transformed into shear. Figure 13 sketches this relationship for different patch pattern for two neighboring patch layers. The overlapping area for each geometry is colored grey. It can be seen that due to the same width b and overlapping length Δx for each type of specimen the resulting overlapping area is equal. Since the overlapping length is only dependent on the patch pattern chosen and the specimen width is also given it can be seen that the overlapping area is independent of the cutting geometry.

Figure 13: Overlapping area for different cutting geometries between to neighboring layer

Inspections of tested specimens are showing that shear failure has been the dominant failure mechanism instead of fiber failure (compare Figure 10). From this it follows that the overlapping length is one of the most important parameter for maximum tensile strength since it tailors the area where shear can be transferred between two neighboring layers. This also explains the similarity between the results for tensile strength and Young's modulus on Figure 8 and Figure 9. The overlap failed before a fiber failure could occur and was therefore the limiting factor. Taking Figure 11 into account an influence of the cutting geometries on tensile strength can be seen but it has a minor effect compared to the overlap length.

Further information gives the strain distribution on the top layer. Figure 14 shows a 30°-specimen before failure. The color distribution from blue to red shows increasing elongation. The fiber discontinuities of the first four layers are marked with a black ellipse. The reason why they can be seen on the top layer is because the resin in each fiber discontinuity has a lower stiffness compared to the fiber so it is receiving the maximum elongation. Those local stiffness differences then are leading to local strain concentration on the top layer. This enlargement of each fiber discontinuity induces stress in the overlap area and thereby accelerating the failure. Each discontinuity can be seen as a seed for a delamination / shear failure.

Figure 14: Strain distribution of 30° specimen before failure (ARAMIS)

An area with low strain (dark blue area) can be seen which shows a beginning delamination. Starting from a discontinuity in the top layer of the specimen the delamination starts to grow towards the clamping support. Since tensile stress is transferred into shear stress between two neighboring layers a moment is induced due to the offset of the normal forces (similar to a single lap joint). For the outer plies this moment cannot be absorbed by covering layers. This leads to a peeling effect which lifts the outer plies and therefore supports the delamination (see Figure 15). On the left picture the delamination in the outer plies can be seen. During testing delaminations are growing and are thereby reducing the cross section of the specimen. Once the tension exceeded the maximum tensile strength the specimen failed catastrophic (right picture). Between the left and the right picture is a time frame of 20/63000 s.

Figure 15: Specimen before final failure (left) and during final failure (right)

The resulting reduction in cross section increases the load in the remaining part of the specimen. Once a discontinuity of a lower ply is revealed due to the delaminated top layer a peeling starts at this point as well. Hence failure starts in the outer plies and then moves towards the middle part of the specimen. This process has an increasing effect when reducing the amount of layers. When having only a limited number of plies the outer plies have a high fraction on the total amount of plies. For example for a 10 plies specimen the two outer plies are make up for 20 % of the total thickness. Once they are lifted the cross section decreases rapidly and thereby weakens the specimen. This effect and strategies to prevent it are currently under further investigation and results will be published in the near future.

5 CONCLUSION

For creating a load path optimized layup design the use of patch material offers advantages compared to continuous fibers when it comes to small radii of curvature of load path trajectory. The tendency towards undulation and fiber wrinkling can be reduced. The patches are positioned in lines without gaps and overlaps. When having curved patch lines gaps and overlaps between two neighboring patches of the same layer occur depending on the shape of the patch. This not only affects the mechanical properties but also leads to locally varying areal weight which can influence the permeability or the surface structure. Typically rectangular patches are used which are leading to the highest degree of gaps and overlaps. One approach to reduce this effect is to use patches where the front part is convex and the end part is concave. This already reduces the degree of overlaps and gaps for curved patch path but not completely. A new approach is to cut the patches according to curvature of the load path. Therefore this study investigated the influence of different cutting angles on tensile strength and Young's modulus and compared the results with the standard rectangular and round patch geometries. No clear dependency whether regarding tensile strength nor Young's modulus could be identified. A tendency for higher strength could be seen for lower cutting angles but due to limited data further research is needed to support this proposition. As a guideline it can be said that based on

this results the cutting geometry can be chosen according to the load path without a significant influence on strength or Young's modulus. Besides this it has to be kept in mind that with increased variability of the cutting angle the complexity of the machine and software tools increases as well. Further investigations have to validate if this development is also economical beneficial.

All tested specimen showed a shear failure behavior. The patches were torn apart without fiber fracture and the shape of the cutting edge was still visible. This confirms the findings from previous investigations that the overlapping length is one of the most important influencing factors on the final mechanical properties of patched laminates. This parameter tailors the area where tension force is transformed into shear. Since the overlap area for each geometry was equal only the shape varied due to the different cut this explains the small differences in mechanical properties between the different cutting geometries.

The investigation was also giving further insight into the failure of patched laminates. Failure starts in the resin rich area between two neighboring patches in the outer plies. Those areas are not covered by another layer and therefore start to peel due to an induced moment. The following delamination of this ply leads to a reduction of cross section of the specimen and reveals discontinuities in lower plies till the specimen fails. This finding is important since for load path optimized designs or local reinforcements the goal is to use as less fiber materials as possible. This effect becomes more important for parts with less layers because the outer plies then have a higher fraction of the total amount of plies. With this behavior the minimum amount of layers is limited which limits the lightweight potential of patched laminates. Therefore this is subject to further investigation with the aim to develop strategies to increase the mechanical properties of patched laminates.

6 REFERENCES

- [1] Lässig R, Eisenhut M, Mathias A, Schulte R, Peters F, Kühmann T et al. Serienproduktion von hochfesten Faserverbundbauteilen: Perspektiven für den deutschen Maschinen- und Anlagenbau; 2012.
- [2] Lukaszewicz D, Ward C, Potter K. The engineering aspects of automated prepreg layup: History, present and future. *Composites Part B: Engineering* 2012;43(3):997–1009.
- [3] Kim BC. Limitations of Fibre Placement Techniques for Variable Angle Tow Composites and their process-induced Defects; 2011.
- [4] Meyer O. Kurzfaser-Preform-Technologie zur kraftflussgerechten Herstellung von Faserverbundbauteilen. Dissertation. Stuttgart; 2008.
- [5] ETH Zürich. inspire ics - Jahrbuch 2012; 2012.
- [6] Wisnom MR. On the Increase in Fracture Energy with Thickness in Delamination of Unidirectional Glass Fibre-Epoxy with Cut Central Plies. *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites* 1992;11(8):897–909.
- [7] Deutsches Institut für Normung e.V. Bestimmung der Zugeigenschaften. 07th ed;83.120(527). Berlin: Beuth Verlag GmbH; 1997.
- [8] Fahrmeir L. Statistik: Der Weg zur Datenanalyse. 7th ed. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer; 2010.